

HYPOCHLORITE OXIDATION OF STARCHES. PART I. OXYGEN UPTAKE IN ABSENCE AND PRESENCE OF CATALYST UNDER VARIED CONDITIONS AND STUDY OF PROPERTIES

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Various starches from cereals, pulses, tubers and roots were treated under different p_H and concentrations of hypochlorite and oxygen uptake were determined.

The reducing value, carboxylic acid content, alkali-labile value of samples, prepared under varied conditions of p_H have been studied. Effect of catalyst on the oxygen uptake has also been studied.

Many investigators¹⁻⁵ studied the oxidation of starch by alkali hypochlorite, but those investigations, however, were restricted to limited varieties of starch available in the market. None of them, however, attempted to study the hypochlorite oxidation in presence of catalysts. Fernbach and Wolff⁶ used copper and iron salts in hydrogen peroxide oxidation of starch. Similarly Dhar and co-workers⁷⁻⁸ studied the induced oxidation of starch by air, using certain salts as inductors and as photocatalysts.

In the present investigation the hypochlorite oxidation has been applied to some varieties of starch, extracted by uniform treatment, from cereals, pulses, tubers and roots grown in Gujarat, and the capacity of different varieties of starches regarding oxygen uptake compared.

EXPERIMENTAL

Extraction of starches from cereals and pulses.—Clean grains were soaked in 0.8% solution of SO_2 and kept for 48 hours, and washed with distilled water. The upper covers of grains were then removed by hand and the inner kernel was carefully crushed in a mortar. Crushed pulp was fractionated by filtering through nylon cloth using excess of distilled water. This process was repeated several times. The product was finally treated with 0.01N-NaOH solution and kept overnight. It was filtered again and washed with distilled water till free of alkali. The product was dried in the sun.

From tubers and roots.—After thorough washing upper covers of the material were removed, and cut into small slices which were soaked in 0.3% sulphur dioxide solution and kept for 48 hours. The rest of the treatment was carried out similarly as above.

Treatment of starches and determination of oxygen uptake.—Starch sample (10 g.) was placed in well-corked flasks outside of which was painted to avoid the decomposition of hypochlorite by light. A buffer solution (50 ml.) corresponding to p_H required after final dilution was added, followed by the calculated volume of hypochlorite solution in order to have the requisite strength at the time of final dilution. A requisite volume of H_2SO_4 solution was added to neutralise the alkalinity of hypochlorite. Finally the whole bulk was made up to 100 ml. with distilled water. The flask was immediately placed in a thermostat at $35^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ and kept there for the scheduled time.

When starches were treated with catalysts, 10 ml. of 1% solution of the catalyst was added in the final mixture before dilution to 100 ml.

In every case the blank experiments were carried out. On completion of the treatment 5 ml. of the clear solution was withdrawn and titrated against $N/50$ -thiosulphate solution after adding 4 ml. of 10% KI and 10 ml. of 10% acetic acid, using starch as an indicator. From the net readings the amount of oxygen consumed was calculated.

Simultaneously the remaining reaction mixture containing starch was filtered under suction and washed with $N/50$ thiosulphate solution and finally with excess of distilled water. When the treatment was carried out in presence of catalysts, the filtered starch was first washed with $N/100$ acetic acid solution and then with thio solution. The starch samples were then desiccated for 12 hours, dried in an oven at 95° for 3 hours and then crushed and passed through 100 mesh sieve and stored in glass-stoppered bottles.

Choice of catalyst.—Nickel sulphate was selected as a catalyst for hypochlorite oxidation as it had no direct effect on decomposition of sodium hypochlorite solution ¹⁰.

The main idea of preparing starch samples by uniform treatment was to obtain as far as possible unmodified natural starches themselves. The starches available in the market are prepared after a good deal of processing which is never uniform for all types of foodstuff. Naturally the sample obtained cannot be taken as the genuine representative of the original starch present in the foodstuff.

Lampitt⁹ and his co-workers have clearly pointed out that the alteration in mechanical operations, such as grinding, changes the nature of the starch molecule itself. The results obtained from samples not uniformly processed cannot be taken as correct data for comparative study. In view of these facts, the starches studied in this investigation were obtained by the same process.

In Table I the values of oxygen uptake in presence and absence of catalysts are recorded. The results obtained with catalysts are expressed as net effect in oxidation in terms of oxygen uptake. It is calculated by deducting the values of oxygen uptake noted in absence of catalyst from those observed in presence of nickel sulphate.

TABLE I

pH 6.95. NaOCl = 2 g. av. Cl₂/litre. Period of treatment = 3 hours.

Cereals :	Oxygen uptake (by 100 g. of starch).		Net effect of catalyst nickel sulphate in terms of oxygen uptake.
	164.0 mg.	10.25 milliatom	
Kodri (<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> , L.)	305.0	19.05	+54.6
Maize (<i>Zea mays</i> , L.)	342.0	21.37	+31.4
Bajri (<i>Pennisetum glaucum</i> , R. Br.)	324.0	20.25	+16.2
Rice (<i>Oriza sativa</i> , L.)	204.0	12.75	+15.9
Bavto (<i>Eleusine Caracana</i> , Gaertn.)	343.0	21.43	+13.0
Cheno (<i>Penicium miliaceum</i> , L.)	346.0	21.62	+ 5.5
Wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i> , L.)	182.0	11.37	-26.24
Juvar (<i>Andropogon sorghum</i> , Brot.)			
Pulses :			
Chana (<i>Cicer arietinum</i> , L.)	186.0	11.625	+35.8
Tuver (<i>Cajanus cajan</i> , Millsp.)	274.0	17.15	+26.8
Maga (<i>Phaseolus mungo</i> , L.)	150.0	9.37	+13.2
Vals (<i>Dolichos lablab</i> , L.)	95.0	5.94	+10.5
Chola (<i>Vigna catjang</i> , Walp.)	212.0	13.25	+ 9.6
Tubers and Roots :			
Shakaria (<i>Ipomoea batatas</i> , Lam.)	90.0	5.62	+70.5
Shingodan (<i>Tropa bispinosa</i> , Roxb.)	101.0	5.31	+56.6
Kand (<i>Dioscorea alata</i> , L.)	99.0	6.18	+ 6.3
Potato (<i>Solanum tuberosum</i> , L.)	157.0	9.81	-15.1

DISCUSSION

With the exception of bavto, juvar and kodri, the starches from the cereals show higher capacity of oxygen uptake than the starches from pulse, tubers and roots.

Tuver and chola starches have higher capacity of oxygen uptake than the cereal starches from bavto, juvar and kodri.

On the whole, the order of capacity of oxygen uptake comes as : cereals > pulses > tubers, roots.

The value for oxygen consumption for tuver starch falls very near to that of maize starch (Table I)

In this connection, it may be pointed out that Nabar and Vyas⁵ in their study regarding the oxygen uptake by the starches from rice, arrowroot, maize and sago observed that the order of capacity for oxygen uptake was as rice > arrowroot > maize > sago.

Regarding the effect of catalyst it is observed that nickel sulphate works in most of the cases as a positive catalyst, but retards the oxidation of juvar and potato.

Those starches which are less oxidised by hypochlorite without catalyst show higher activity in presence of nickel sulphate. For instance, kodri and shakaria starches, which are less subject to direct oxidation, show here the highest susceptibility in their group. In case of cereals, tubers and roots the order of susceptibility is practically reversed.

Effect of pH and concentration.—The results obtained for maize and tuber starches with different pH are shown in Fig. 1 and the results for variation in concentration in Table II.

TABLE II

Av. Cl ₂ /litre.	pH = 6.95. Time = 3 hrs.		
	Oxygen consumption by 100 g. of starch (in milliatoms).		
	Maize.	Tuver.	Shingodan.
1. g.	12.65	11.34	6.76
3.	29.37	20.57	12.51
4.	33.91	20.97	15.45
5.	36.96	23.74	18.17

FIG. 1

The general behaviour of maize starch and tuber starch appears from Fig. 1 to be similar as regards the oxygen uptake at different pH. The disposition of the curves is practically the same. In the alkaline medium the capacity for oxygen uptake is higher than what it is in the acidic medium. With the increase in concentration of the hypochlorite, oxygen consumption increases; however, the increase is not uniform.

Properties of modified and unmodified starches.—During the hypochlorite oxidation it is supposed that the primary -CH₂OH group is converted into -CHO group, which finally passes into -COOH group.

Thus it is quite natural that the oxidised samples would show conspicuous change in the properties when compared with the unoxidised samples, and therefore the reducing value, carboxylic acid content, alkali-labile value and the viscosities have been studied.

Normally it may be expected that the total oxygen consumed could be accounted for by the chemical properties developed in the samples. However, Nabar and Vyas⁵ found that the oxygen consumed was not only utilised for the formation of aldehydic and acidic groups but also for certain side reactions. The possible side reactions are the oxidation of the secondary alcoholic groups to the carboxylic acid group and the induced hydrolysis of the glucosidic linkage by virtue of the instability of hydroxy-acid thus produced. Moreover, Nabar and Vyas⁵ observed irregular relationship between fall in viscosity and oxygen uptake.

Similarly the relationship between reducing power and the oxygen uptake has been found to be fairly irregular. The argument forwarded in that connection was that the oxygen uptake from hypochlorite was not solely used for the formation of reducing and acidic groups but also consumed for further degradation products which finally disappeared as carbon dioxide and water or as water-soluble products.

Keeping the above generalisation in view, the properties of the samples, prepared under varied conditions, were studied. The determination of the properties of the modified and unmodified samples were carried out by the standard methods. The determination of reducing values was carried out by the method used by Richardson¹¹. Carboxylic acid content was determined by the method of Neale¹². Alkali-labile value was determined by the well known hypoidide method of T aylor¹³. The viscosity determinations were carried out by the use of Ostwald viscometer. The results obtained are recorded in Table III.

The reducing values developed in different varieties of starch, from the results in Table III, do not show any regular relationship with the amount of oxygen uptake. Except maize, tuver and vala, in all the varieties the reducing values increased when the oxidation was carried out in absence of the catalyst.

In case of maize, tuver and vala the reducing values, which are respectively 7.608, 1.522 and 1.369, have been reduced to 0.761, 1.065 and 1.065. This shows that in these varieties of starches, the oxidation has taken a course wherein no new aldehydic groups have increased but the carboxylic groups have been formed from the aldehydic groups already present. That is why the carboxylic acid content in maize has gone from 0.0 to 2.0, in tuver from 0.0 to 4.48, and in vala from 0.8 to 1.68.

TABLE III

Variety.	Reducing value Cu_2O in g. for 100 g. of starch.			Carboxylic acid content in m. e.			Alkali-labile value.			Viscosity in centipoises of 2% soln.		
	a.	b.	c.	a.	b.	c.	a.	b.	c.	a.	b.	c.
Kodri	0.913	0.913	1.826	0.000	3.600	2.240	11.20	20.30	23.45	6.267	2.334	1.394
Maize	7.608	0.761	2.130	0.000	2.000	2.200	16.10	16.80	14.52	6.710	2.979	2.836
Bajri	1.369	1.521	0.913	0.000	4.160	4.840	9.10	18.90	19.95	8.115	2.134	2.090
Rice	1.826	2.587	1.217	0.000	3.800	2.000	10.50	19.95	19.90	3.565	2.345	1.964
Bavta	1.065	2.282	1.674	0.000	2.800	2.120	9.45	21.00	23.10	6.045	2.409	1.543
Cheno	1.217	1.369	0.000	0.800	2.480	3.800	15.05	19.95	22.92	7.849	1.536	1.592
Wheat	1.674	1.826	0.456	0.040	2.280	4.160	13.65	16.45	16.45	3.523	2.629	2.359
Juvar	1.522	2.739	0.913	0.800	3.880	2.000	10.85	18.55	9.45	6.483	2.227	2.012
Chana	0.760	2.130	1.065	0.000	1.800	2.600	9.45	20.75	24.15	2.280	1.921	1.543
Tuver	1.522	1.065	0.456	0.000	1.480	2.000	10.50	17.50	15.22	3.792	2.430	2.097
Maga	1.065	1.369	2.434	0.000	2.600	2.600	6.30	17.15	20.55	4.178	2.686	1.898
Vala	1.369	1.065	1.978	0.800	1.680	2.000	7.70	10.15	19.95	4.210	2.510	2.254
Chola	1.065	1.826	1.522	0.040	3.760	3.400	11.90	20.65	25.20	9.441	1.915	1.661
Shakaria	1.369	2.282	0.304	0.800	3.000	0.800	9.45	18.20	12.95	12.920	2.048	1.596
Shingodan	1.217	1.978	1.978	0.800	4.040	3.480	14.35	23.10	23.10	3.899	1.943	1.525
Kand	0.456	2.130	1.065	0.000	4.400	3.960	8.05	20.30	21.70	7.206	1.841	1.805
Potato	0.760	1.674	2.587	0.030	2.760	2.400	10.85	20.30	19.25	31.840	1.792	1.898

a—unoxidised; b—oxidised without catalyst; c—oxidised with NiSO_4 .

In other varieties of starches there is an increase in reducing value as well as carboxylic acid content. This can be ascribed to the simultaneous formation of (i) new aldehydic groups from free $-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ groups present in the branched chain of the starch molecules and (ii) carboxylic groups from the existing aldehydic groups. The increase in the reducing value suggests that the rate of the formation of aldehydic groups is greater than the rate of the formation of the $-\text{COOH}$ groups.

The alkali-labile values in the majority of the starches have increased and indicate that the oxidation treatment in the presence and absence of the catalyst has brought about the dissociation of the chains as suggested by Taylor and Keresztesy¹⁴.

The slight decrease in the alkali-labile value in case of maize and tuver starch can be ascribed to the slight hydrolytic breakdown of the glucosidic links during the oxidation treatment. The alkali-labile values obtained with respect to starches, oxidised in the presence and the absence of nickel sulphate, clearly differ. This fact clearly suggests that the catalyst has a definite influence on the mode of oxidation. The relation between the alkali-labile values and the amount of oxygen uptake does not show any fair regularity.

The viscosity has decreased in the oxidised samples as expected. The values of the viscosity of the samples oxidised in the presence of the catalyst are, however, lower than those of the samples oxidised in the absence of the

catalyst. This clearly points out that the catalyst does influence the course of oxidation. The relationship between the viscosity and oxygen uptake is not regular (vide Table III).

Properties of oxidised starches and other factors.—It has been observed by Nabar and Vyas⁵ that the properties developed in oxidised starches bear some relationship with the experimental conditions such as p_H and concentration. In view of this fact the properties of selected modified starches, which were treated under different conditions, were determined. The results are shown in Tables IV and V.

TABLE IV
Effect of p_H .

p_H .	Maize.			Tuver.		
	a.	b.	c.	a.	b.	c.
5.49	0.152	5.28	18.20	0.304	3.000	19.60
6.39	0.152	2.20	18.90	1.521	2.000	21.00
6.95	0.761	2.00	16.80	1.065	1.480	17.50
8.20	0.304	2.60	19.95	0.456	2.920	18.20
9.15	0.456	3.60	19.95	0.912	3.300	19.60

a=reducing value ; b=carboxylic acid content ; c=alkali-labile value ;

TABLE V
Effect of concentration.

Av. Cl_2 (g./litre).	Reducing value.			Alkali-labile value.			Carboxylic acid content.		
	M.	T.	S.	M.	T.	S.	M.	T.	S.
1	0.913	0.152	0.913	14.70	13.30	19.60	1.44	1.12	1.80
2	0.761	1.065	1.978	16.80	17.50	23.10	2.00	1.48	4.84
3	1.217	1.217	1.826	19.95	22.40	27.30	2.00	1.80	3.40
4	2.587	3.804	3.499	23.10	26.25	30.15	4.20	5.04	4.32
5	0.761	3.195	4.260	24.85	31.15	30.15	4.68	5.84	5.20

M—maize ; T—tuver ; S—shingodan.

From the above results it appears that both the starches show the minimum values of carboxylic acid content and alkali-labile value at p_H 6.95. The reducing values in case of tuver and maize become maximum at a concentration of 4 g. av. Cl_2 /litre, whereas the value for shingodan tends to rise even beyond concentration of 5 g. av. Cl_2 /litre. There is no linear relationship between the reducing value and the concentration. The disposition of curves shown in Fig. 2 leads to following conclusions.

During the oxidation of starch two reactions: (i) $-CH_2OH \rightarrow CHO$ and (ii) $-CHO \rightarrow COOH$ proceed simultaneously. However, due to the domination of one over the other, the effect of only one reaction is observed. The conspicuous domination of the first reaction shows the rise in reducing value

(as observed in tuber and shingodan) up to a particular stage; whereas in case of maize starch the second reaction dominates and shows the fall in reducing power. The original sample of maize starch has the reducing value 7.608 and it suggests that there are a number of CHO groups available for conversion into-COOH groups, and hence, an increase in the reducing groups cannot be apparent.

FIG. 2

The relation between alkali-labile value and the concentration in all the three varieties is linear.

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